

IMPACT OF FILAMENT PREPARATION ON THE PERFORMANCE OF FDM 3D PRINTED COMPOSITES

Lizhe He^{1*}, Chenkai Zhu², Xiaoling Liu³ and Chris D. Rudd⁴

¹ University of Nottingham, Ningbo, China. Lizhe.He@nottingham.edu.cn

² University of Nottingham, Ningbo, China. Chenkai.Zhu1@nottingham.edu.cn

³ University of Nottingham, Ningbo, China. Xiaoling.Liu@nottingham.edu.cn

⁴ James Cook University Singapore, Singapore. chris.rudd@jcu.edu.au

Corresponding author: Lizhe He (Lizhe.He@nottingham.edu.cn)

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ABSTRACT

Filament preparation is a prerequisite procedure in composites 3D printing based on fused deposition modelling (FDM). However, the impact of filament preparation on the properties of resultant FDM products has not been reported. In this work, the short glass fibre/poly lactide (GF/PLA) composites were made into filaments via two different workflows: a 3-step workflow of melt compounding – granulation – extrusion, or a 2-step workflow of material blending and extrusion. The filaments were then used for FDM. For the 3-step workflow, fibres were apparently shortened after melt compounding, especially for the ~ 4 mm fibre bundles that were shortened by > 90%. The 2-step workflow worked smoothly to prepare filaments containing ~ 0.1 mm fibres. However, the ~ 4 mm fibre bundles led to jammed extrusion and the 2-step workflow was frequently interrupted. In contrast to 3-step workflow, the 2-step workflow only led to <10% length reduction of fibres.

FDM products made with different filaments were examined for the fibre length/orientation as well as their flexural properties. More than 55% of short fibres aligned with the FDM extrusion paths, and over 80% fibres were parallel with the horizontally deposited layers. The FDM products made with 2-step filaments showed superior strength and stiffness, as higher degree of fibre alignment and greater fibre length led to improved flexural properties. Greater fibre length was beneficial for higher strength and stiffness of the additive-manufactured polymer composites, and the fibre length was more influenced by the filament preparation than the final additive manufacturing process.

1 INTRODUCTION

There is an increasing demand for polymer materials that can be applied in the additive manufacturing process, while possessing enhanced mechanical properties for engineering application. Reinforcing the polymers with fibres has been intensively researched for the stated purpose [1]. It is reported that composites reinforced with continuous fibres (e.g. carbon fibres [2], jute [3], Kevlar® [4] and flax [5]) possess excellent strength and stiffness that are one order higher than polymer counterparts. Nevertheless, the additive manufacturing of continuous fibre reinforced composites usually requires specifically designed/modified apparatus for both the feedstock fabrication and additive manufacturing process, and the freedom of manufacturing process is somehow limited by the continuous fibre reinforcements. In contrast, short fibre allows the reinforced polymer composites to be smoothly processed by conventional additive manufacturing device, substituting the pure polymer feedstocks for the fabrication of products with slightly improved mechanical properties [6].

A possible strategy to further enhance the mechanical properties of short fibre reinforced composites is to increase the fibre length while maintaining good compatibility with the additive manufacturing process. It is well reported that the greater fibre length is beneficial to the stiffness and (more apparently) strength of composites [7,8]. In previous studies, however, the role of fibre length in additive-manufactured composites was seldom investigated as an independent factor, as the fibre length was indirectly manipulated (e.g. reducing the fibre length by increasing the fibre loading) [9]. In addition,

the fibre length profile of composites from the feedstock preparation workflow to additive manufacturing has not been studied. In this sense, a clear understanding of how the average fibre length changes during the processes of feedstock preparation and additive manufacturing shall be developed, and the relationship between fibre length and resultant composite properties needs investigation. The findings may inspire new practices of handling the fibre reinforcements for increased length in the additive-manufactured products, and consequently enhanced composites properties.

In this work, glass fibres (GF) reinforced polylactide (PLA) were made into filamentous FDM feedstock by two procedures: the 3-step workflow consists of melt-compounding, granulation and filament extrusion, or a 2-step workflow consists of material blending and filament extrusion. The filaments were then used for additive manufacturing by the FDM 3D printer. Fibre length profile during the filament preparation workflow and additive manufacturing was developed to track the changes of fibre length after each process. Finally, the impact of fibre length on structural/mechanical properties of the additive-manufactured composites were investigated.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

E-glass fibres (GF) with different average length were supplied by Corker Chemical Engineering, China. The fibre A and fibre B were milled glass fibres. The average length (as examined under the microscope) was 0.099 mm and 0.122 mm, respectively. The fibre C was in the form of short, chopped fibre bundles with an average length of 4.016 mm. Polylactide (PLA) grains of Ingeo 4032D (NatureWorks®, U.S.A.) was the matrix material. All materials were dehydrated in an oven under 70 °C for 3 hours prior to use. Dichloromethane (AR, Sinopharm Chemical Reagents®, China) served as the organic solvent to dissolve the PLA and extract fibres from the composites.

2.2 3-step filament preparation

The 3-step filament preparation workflow contains three procedures: melt compounding, granulation and filament extrusion, see Figure 1. For the melt compounding, GF and PLA grains were weighted at the ratio of 20:80, then added into the mixing chamber of a Banbury mixer (ZG-3L; Zhenggong®, China). The GF/PLA mixture was softened for 10 minutes under 205 °C and then compounded at 20 rpm for another 10 minutes. This procedure produced homogenized, composite free-forms.

The resultant composite free-form was granulated into pellets using a plastic granulator (DJT300; Dingjun®, China) equipped with a 6-mm mesh. Finally, the composite pellets were fed into the single screw extruder (Model C-2; Wellzoom®, China) to extrude the filaments for additive manufacturing. The temperatures of the preheat zone and the 2 mm extrusion die were 213 °C and 208 °C, respectively, and the screw rotation rate was 30 rpm. Pure PLA and GF/PLA composite filaments with a diameter of 1.75 ± 0.2 mm were extruded as a result.

Figure 1. 3-step filament preparation workflow

2.3 2-step filament preparation

The 2-step filament preparation workflow is depicted in Figure 2. For the physical blending process, the GF and PLA grains were weighted at the ratio of 20:80, then added into a blender (DY1000; Xinyuan®, China) with blunt blades for 5 minutes of blending. The resultant GF/PLA mixture was directly fed into the single screw extruder to extrude the composite filaments, following the same extrusion protocol as stated in 2.2.

Figure 2. 2-step filament preparation workflow

2.4 Fused deposition modelling (FDM)

The composite filaments described in session 2.2 or 2.3 were used to manufacture the 3-point bending specimens ($80 \times 10 \times 4$ mm³), using the FDM 3D printer (Ultimaker 2+, Ultimaker®, Netherlands) equipped with a 0.4 mm nozzle. The nozzle/build plate temperatures were 235 °C and 60°C, respectively. The defined layer height was 0.2 mm and the default printing speed was 2400 mm/min. The infill of specimens was in the 0° (parallel with the long edge of specimen/Y-axis in Figure 3) rectilinear pattern at 100% infill percentage.

2.5 Fibre length measurement

The length of fibres were measured from microscopic images. Prior to imaging, ~2 g of composites were dissolved in dichloromethane. The resultant solution was spread on a glass slide with a rubber roll and left in fume hood for 10 minutes of solvent evaporation. The fibres within the film and the as-received fibres were examined under a microscope (NE930; NexScope®, China). For each composites, the lengths of more than 1000 fibres were analyzed using the ScopeImage (freeware, version 10.4) software.

2.6 Fibre orientation characterization

The orientation profile of fibres within FDM products (3-point bending specimens) was characterized based on two-dimensional microscopic imaging in two planes: a transversal plane (red) parallel with the X-Y plane, and a frontal (green) plane parallel with the Y-Z plane, as depicted in Figure 3. The specimens were embedded in colourless acrylic resin (G00548; Kaopin®, China), then ground-polished on a polisher (YMP-1; Yuzhou®, China) using 2000-grit sanding paper. The polished surfaces were examined under the microscope, with the angles (θ in transversal plane, and φ in the frontal plane) between fibres and Y-axis measured using Image-Pro Plus (Version 6.0.0.2, Media Cybernetics®, U.S.A.). More than 1000 fibres were sampled. A simple orientation function applied by Chen et al. [10] is used to describe the alignment degree:

$$f_{\theta} = \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\cos(\theta)_i}{n} \right)^2$$

where i is the number of a single fibre and n is the total count of fibres. The equation was also applied to ϕ . The range of f is $[0,1]$. A greater f indicates a higher degree of fibres alignment with the Y-axis.

Figure 3. The 3-Point bending test specimen ($80 \times 10 \times 4 \text{ mm}^3$) in a Cartesian coordinate, with the length, width and height corresponding to Y, X and Z axis. Transversal plane (red) and frontal plane (green) within the composites were created by ground polishing.

2.7 3-Point bending tests

3-point bending tests of FDM products were carried out in accordance with ISO 14125:1998 testing standard, using the universal testing machine (E45.105; MTS[®], U.S.A.) equipped with a 50 kN load cell. The cross-head speed was 2 mm/min. 5 replicates were tested for each type of composites.

2.8 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

The fractured surfaces of composite filaments and FDM products were coated with 10 nm conductive gold layer in a vacuum film deposition system (SCD-500; Leica Microsystems[®], Germany). The coated samples were imaged using a scanning electron microscope (Sigma VP; Zeiss[®], Germany) under the SE2 secondary electron mode.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Fabrication of composite filaments

The composites filaments were fabricated via two workflow. Filaments containing all 3 types of fibres were successfully made with the 3-step workflow. The 2-step workflow worked smoothly with the powder-like fibre A and B with length of $\sim 0.1 \text{ mm}$. However, the same process was not compatible with the fibre C - the extrusion process was frequently interrupted, and nodes within the extruded filaments were seen. Further examination under SEM confirmed the nodes to be densely aggregated, randomly aligned fibres, as depicted in Figure 4. A possible reason was that the 2-step workflow lack sufficient shearing procedures to disintegrate the densely packed fibre bundles into loose fibres. Consequently, the fibre bundles jammed the screw and could not be evenly dispersed in PLA melts.

Figure 4. 2-step prepared Fibre C/PLA composite filaments with smoothly extruded section (marked as “A”), and a short, completely opaque node (marked as “B”), and the SEM images of fractured surfaces at the two positions.

3.2 Fibre length of filaments and composites after each process

The fibre length profile at different stages of the 3-step workflow is shown in Table 1. In general, the fibre lengths were reduced after each process. During the melt compounding process, the fibres compounded in polymer melts were vigorously sheared by the mixing rotor. In result, the fibres were severely damaged due to fibre-fibre interaction, abrasion against the device (e.g. rotor and the inner wall of mixing chamber) and the dragging by the viscous polymer melts [11,12]. The length reduction was more apparent for longer fibres, especially for the fibre C that was catastrophically shortened by more than 90%. This was possibly due to stronger fibre-fibre interaction among longer fibres, which had a higher probability of interacting with each other during the melt compounding. In the following granulation process, the composite free-forms were vigorously broken down into pellets, during which the fibres embedded in solidified PLA matrix were further shortened by the mechanical break-down process. The length reduction rate was the second greatest among the 4 procedures (melt compounding, granulation, filament extrusion and FDM) investigated.

The composite pellets were fed in the extruder to produce filamentous feedstocks for 3D printer. The factors leading to fibre shortening were the same as the melt compounding process. A much lower degree of shortening was seen, as there was no vigorous shearing involved. Finally, the filaments were used for additive manufacturing (FDM). The fibre-fibre interaction as well as the friction between fibres and the inner surface of the nozzle only modestly shortened the fibres.

	As-received / mm	Free-form / mm	Pellets / mm	Filaments / mm	FDM Products/ mm
Fibre A	0.099±0.070 (/)	0.086±0.061 (12.45%)	0.083±0.054 (3.94%)	0.081±0.056 (2.77%)	0.082±0.058 (-1.40%)
Fibre B	0.122±0.081 (/)	0.106±0.075 (13.11%)	0.097±0.072 (8.38%)	0.094±0.058 (3.24%)	0.093±0.064 (1.06%)
Fibre C	4.013±0.131 (/)	0.349±0.225 (91.32%)	0.291±0.192 (16.57%)	0.255±0.193 (12.53%)	0.251±0.191 (1.48%)

Table 1. Average fibre length (\pm standard deviation), and length reduction rates comparing to the previous stage (in brackets) of the 3-step workflow and following FDM

Similarly, the fibre length profile of composites after 2-step filament preparation and subsequent additive manufacturing is listed in Table 2. Without the vigorous melt compounding and granulation process, the fibres in 2-step prepared filaments maintained a greater length. Consequently, the FDM products made with these filaments contained longer fibres, as indicated by the fibre length distribution in Figure 5 and 6 respectively.

Type of fibres	As-received / mm	Filaments / mm	FDM Products/ mm
Fibre A	0.099±0.070 (/)	0.097±0.071 (2.02%)	0.096±0.062 (1.03%)
Fibre B	0.122±0.081 (/)	0.114±0.080 (6.56%)	0.112±0.084 (1.75%)
Fibre C	4.013±0.131 (/)	N/A	N/A

Table 2. Average fibre lengths (\pm standard deviation), and length reduction rates comparing to the previous stage (in brackets) of the 2-step workflow and following FDM

Figure 5. The length distribution of fibre A as virgin (as-received) fibres and fibres in FDM products.

Figure 6. The length distribution of fibre B as virgin (as-received) fibres and fibres in FDM products.

3.2 Fibre orientation characterization

The orientation profile of fibres within FDM products was analysed by the angles between fibres and Y-axis measured from microscope images. In the transversal plane, the angle θ indicates the alignment of fibres with the extruded paths: the closer to 0° , the better the fibres were aligned with the paths. The results are shown in Table 3 and Figure 7. For FDM products made with 3-step filaments, a broad distribution of θ was found for fibre A. As average fibre length increased, the distribution curves were narrowed with a sharper, higher peak around 0° . More than $>55\%$ (number fraction) of the short fibres showed good alignment with the extrusion path. The fibres were preferably aligned during the FDM process due to flow-induced orientation: as the polymer melts are extruded from the convergent nozzle, the flow of polymer melts induces orientation of short fibres, aligning them with the flowing direction [13,14].

There are two findings from the f_θ profile in this study that need to be further investigated. First, the results suggest a higher degree of fibre orientation when the average fibre length (and consequently, aspect ratio) increases. However, the finding is not strongly supported in recent studies where there was only slight differences among the second-order tensors indicating short fibre orientation in FDM products [9,13]. Second, the composites fabricated with 2-step filaments showed a significantly higher degree of alignment. The fibre orientation profile is reported to be determined by fibre-fibre interaction and shear viscosity of composites melts, which are further influenced by fibre concentration, fibre length/aspect ratio and the molecular weight of polymer matrices [15]. Therefore, the rheology of these composites during the FDM extrusion process shall be systematically studied to specifically verify the findings in this study.

The angles between fibres and Y-axis (denoted as φ) in the frontal plane were also examined as they indicate the compliance of fibres with the transversal planes deposited during the FDM process. The results in Table 3 and Figure 8 showed that fibres in all composites showed good alignment with the Y-axis (number fraction $> 80\%$ and $f_\varphi > 0.9$ in all cases), and the fibres with $\varphi > 45^\circ$ were rarely seen. The result suggests that most of the fibres were aligned in the horizontal plane deposited during the FDM process, while a small portion of the fibres were slightly tilted. As the polymer flow was vertically extruded out of the nozzle and deposited in the horizontal planes, some of the fibres were tilted as the combination of vertical and horizontal motion [13].

Type of Fibre	Filament fabrication	f_θ	f_φ
Fibre A	3-step	0.7318	0.9314
Fibre B	3-step	0.8121	0.9258
Fibre C	3-step	0.8530	0.9663
Fibre A	2-step	0.9056	0.9758
Fibre B	2-step	0.9439	0.9763

Table 3. The orientation function of different FDM products. f_θ describes the alignment of fibres with FDM extruded paths, and f_φ describes the alignment of fibres with and the horizontally deposited plane.

Figure 7. The distribution of θ (angles between fibres and Y-axis in transversal planes) in FDM products.

Figure 8. The distribution of φ (angles between fibres and Y-axis in frontal planes) in FDM products.

3.3 3-Point bending tests

Figure 9 shows the flexural strength and modulus of all FDM products made with different filaments. The incorporation of fibre reinforcement led to reduced strength in composites, suggesting that the fibres were being too short and below the critical length [8]. For FDM products made with 3-step prepared filaments, the flexural strength and modulus were found highest with fibre C as reinforcement, followed by fibre B, and lowest for fibre A. The strength and stiffness were found in 20 wt% fibre C reinforced composites were 88.70 ± 4.26 MPa and 6.39 ± 0.33 GPa, respectively, and the modulus was 103% higher than pure PLA counterparts.

The mechanical properties of short fibre reinforced composites are strongly influenced by the distribution of fibre orientation and fibre length [12]. Referring to Figure 3, the bending load induces compressive (upper half of specimen) and tensile (lower half of specimen) stress along the Y-axis. Therefore, the composites were stronger and stiffer in this direction, as more fibres were bear the stress in their axial direction [14]. Meanwhile, the greater length allows higher stress to be developed at the centre of the fibre, therefore improving the load-bearing capacity of reinforced composites [14]. In result, the mechanical properties of FDM products were found highest in composites with longer, better-aligned fibre C, in contrast to shorter, more randomly oriented fibre A.

With the same type of fibre reinforcements, FDM products made with 2-step prepared filaments had significantly superior flexural strength and modulus, as confirmed by statistical analysis (two-tailed $p < 0.05$, unpaired t-tests). Optimal results were found from fibre B/PLA composites. The strength of 89.53 ± 2.88 MPa and modulus of 5.57 ± 0.30 GPa were 9% and 20% higher than fibre B/PLA composites produced with 3-step filaments, respectively. Similarly, the greater fibre length and a higher degree of fibre orientation accounted for the enhanced mechanical properties. The higher mechanical properties might also be a result of less thermal degradation of PLA. During filament making, the PLA in 3-step workflow were melted twice (melt-compounding and filament extrusion), in contrast to only one melting history (filament extrusion) in the 2-step workflow. The extra melting process might have induced undesired degradation of PLA, lowering the molecular weight and consequently mechanical properties of resultant composites. A closer examination on the molecular weight is required to verify this hypothesis.

Figure 9. Flexural strength and modulus of FDM products

3.4 SEM imaging of fractured surfaces

Fractured surfaces of FDM products were imaged under SEM and shown in Figure 10. For all FDM products made with 3-step prepared filaments, the fibres were evenly distributed within the composites. A considerable fraction of fibres was pulled out, leaving pits in the polymer matrix. This finding suggests that the interfacial strength was rather low to fully utilize the load-bearing capacity of fibres.

Figure 10. Fractured surfaces of FDM products made with different filaments and containing different types of fibre reinforcements.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the GF/PLA composites were fabricated into filaments and used for fused deposition modelling. A 3-step filament preparation workflow of melt compounding, granulation and filament extrusion worked smoothly with all starting materials. However, the melt compounding process resulted in severe damage and shortening of glass fibres. In contrast, the 2-step filament preparation workflow only worked for ~0.1 mm short fibres, but resulted in minimal fibre length reduction. The FDM products of different filaments were examined for the fibre length/orientation inside and the flexural mechanical properties. Products made with 2-step prepared filaments showed higher degree of fibre alignment with extruded paths and the horizontally deposited layers, which resulted in higher flexural strength and modulus. The results indicate the potential benefit of 2-step, direct filament extrusion workflow, but also call for further works to improve the compatibility and reliability of this process.

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